

Himanshu SINGH

CAREER OBJECTIVE

To use my skills in mechanical engineering and design to create innovative and practical solutions. The aim to contribute to industries and communities by driving growth and positive change.

PERSONAL DATA

DATE OF BIRTH: 10 August 1999
PRESENT ADDRESS: Karnataka, India

LINKEDIN: /himanshu-singh-mech
ORCID: 0009-0008-0098-8000

EDUCATION

- AUG,2022 - MAY,2024 M.Tech in MACHINE DESIGN AND ANALYSIS
National Institute of Technology, Rourkela, Odisha
GPA: 8.39/10
- JULY,2018 - MAY,2022 B.Tech in MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra, Ranchi, Jharkhand
GPA: 7.48/10
- JUN,2017 Intermediate in Science and Maths
Krishna Public School, Raipur, Chhattisgarh
PERCENTAGE: 77.4 %
- JUN,2015 Matriculation
D.A.V Public School, Majhgawan, Panna, Madhya Pradesh
GPA: 7.4/10

PATENTS / PUBLICATIONS

- FEB, 2025 | Book Chapter: MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF 3D PRINTED PARTS - WILEY
In: Biswas, S., Singh, H., Khatu, J. U. (2025). Metal Additive Manufacturing: Principles, Techniques, and Applications, Edited by R. Rajasekar, Amir Mostafaei, C. Moganapriya, P. Sathish Kumar. Scrivener Publishing, ISBN: 9781394287628
- SEP, 2024 | Application No. 202431068691 - THE PATENT OFFICE, INDIA
FILAMENT EXTRUSION SYSTEM FOR 3D PRINTING APPLICATIONS AND METHOD FOR PRODUCING COMPOSITE FILAMENT FOR 3D PRINTING. Khatu, J. U., Singh, H., Suna, K., Biswas, S., Sen, S. (Filed Sep 20,2024).

PROJECTS

MAY,2023 - MAY,2024	Final year Project at NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, ROURKELA <i>DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF A PORTABLE FILAMENT EXTRUDER FOR FUSED DEPOSITION MODELING BASED 3D PRINTER</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Developed a portable filament extruder to produce 3D printing filament for FDM based 3D printers.- Aiming to reduce material costs and enhance the flexibility of the material selection.- Completed successfully with excellent outcomes with filed a patent in IP India. Under faculty mentor Prof. Dr. S. Biswas.
JAN-MAY, 2022	Project at BIRLA INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, MESRA <i>DESIGN AND SIMULATION OF FOUR BAR MECHANISM FOR BICYCLE SUSPENSION</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Design and simulate the performance of a four bar mechanism to enhance the shock absorption and overall ride comfort of bicycles.- Aimed at improving bicycle suspension systems by designing a more efficient and durable four bar linkage mechanism- Completed successfully with excellent outcomes. Under faculty mentor Prof. Dr. Richa Pandey. Group of 3 members.

WORK EXPERIENCE

JUN - JUL, 2021	Research Intern at INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, INDORE <i>VIBRATION CONTROL OF ELECTRIC VEHICLES.</i> <p>Conducted a study on mechanical noises and vibrations under Prof. Dr. Anand Parey, focusing on noise control in electric vehicles using NVH methods. Awarded an e-certificate for the Research Internship.</p>
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SKILLS

LANGUAGES:	Hindi English
TOOLS & TECHNOLOGIES:	SOLIDWORKS Fusion 360 ANSYS - Fluent, Structural MATLAB C++/C SQL Adobe Photoshop and Premiere Pro MS Office- Word, PowerPoint, Excel
SOFT SKILL:	Leadership Team-Player Work Ethic Positive Thinking Adaptability Problem Solving

CERTIFICATIONS

MAR, 2023	Certified Solidworks Associate (CSWA - Mechanical Design)
SEPT, 2020	Modeling and Design for Mechanical Engineers with Fusion 360
JUL, 2020	Intro. to Mechanical Engineering Design and Manuf. with Fusion 360

ACHIEVEMENTS / AWARDS

2023	Intra Hall Chess Tournament (NITR)	WINNER
2023	Intra Hall Double Badminton Tournament (NITR)	RUNNER UP
2022	Intra Hall Double Badminton Tournament (NITR)	WINNER
2021	SQL in HackerRank Platform	SILVER LEVEL BADGES
2016	Inter School Single Badminton Tournament	WINNER
2015	CBSE Cluster National Badminton Championship (West Zone)	QUARTER FINALIST

EXTRA CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

Club Activities - Fine Arts Society, BIT MESRA

Senior Executive Member - 2021 - 2022

- Overseeing the upcoming Events. -Generate ideas to publicity of club as well as club events.
- Conduct Team meeting to resolve general problem as well as personal issues too.

Design Head - 2020 - 2021

- Tutoring Graphic Design (Branding & Publishing) to freshers. -Prepare rough drafts and present ideas. -Finalising poster designs.

Volunteer Experience

- BITOTSAV'20 (annual festival), BIT Mesra (part of the Publicity and Design Team)
- PANTHEON'19 (Tech- Fest), BIT Mesra (Part of Publicity Team)

INTERESTS

Badminton | Quad- Pilot | CAD Designing | Graphic Designing (Publishing & Branding) | Video Editing.

Declaration: I hereby certify that the details provided above are true to the best of my knowledge and belief.

Latest by 20/02/2025